

Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D7.6

Report about the demonstration in Alicante

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Responsible Partner:	UA, EUCENTRE, NORSAR, ARU, B80, NTC
Reviewers:	Alireza Azarbakht & Tina Kaschwich
Version:	1.0
Date:	30 May 2022
Distribution level:	Public

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Date	Version	Editor	Comments

LIST OF PARTNERS

Participant	Name	Country
NOR	Stiftelsen NORSAR	Norway
DEL	Stichting Deltares	Netherlands
KNMI	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut	Netherlands
BRGM	Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières	France
EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
UIce	Haskoli Islands (University of Iceland)	Iceland
EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
UStr	University of Strathclyde	UK
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	Germany
UA	Universidad de Alicante	Spain
ARU	Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation	UK
UNIBG	Università degli Studi di Bergamo	Italy
UCL	University College London	UK
INFP	Institutul National de Cercetare si Dezvoltare pentru Fizica Pamantului	Romania
YET	YetItMoves S.r.l.	Italy
GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
UPat	Panepistimio Patron (University of Patras)	Greece

GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
EEW	Earthquake Early Warning
EMS-98	European Macroseismic Scale Intensity
FWCR	Forecasting – Early Warning – Consequence Prediction – Response
GEM	Global Earthquake Model foundation
GMPE	Ground Motion Prediction Equation
IGN	National Geographic Institute
OEF	Operational Earthquake Forecasting
PGA	Peak Ground Acceleration

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RRE	Rapid Response to Earthquake
RS4D	RaspberryShake 4D
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats
TB	TestBed
UPM	Technical University of Madrid
USGS	United States Geological Survey

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1 INTRODUCTION

The TURNkey FWCR (Forecasting – Early Warning – Consequence Prediction – Response) platform is a multi-sensor-based earthquake information system, facilitating earthquake forecasting and enabling early warning and rapid response actions. The FWCR platform has been designed to be based on low-cost multi-sensor units and a cloud-based computer system, which can be distributed as a fully operational TURNkey product to public authorities/decision-makers (e.g., disaster management authorities, political authorities), first responders (civil protection, search-and-rescue teams, emergency medical services), private companies (including operators of critical infrastructure) and general businesses (including the insurance industry). TURNkey platform's overall concept is shown in Figure 1. This platform can assist the identified stakeholders to react at the earliest stage to earthquake events, to reduce the direct and indirect (follow-up) impacts and consequences.

Figure 1. General concept of the TURNkey FWCR platform

This document describes the demonstration of the platform to Spanish stakeholders, without pre-knowledge of the platform, and to the international stakeholders who have been present in the TB demonstration. The main goal of the demo is to carry out a simulation for the province of Alicante (as an example of low probability yet high impact of a moderate earthquake on the buildings, infrastructures and inhabitants) in order to: a) show to the stakeholders that the developed solution can be deployed and tested quickly in any city, b) check that the results provided by the tool can be easily understood and used by stakeholder and the citizens, and c) check that the developed solution can be incorporated in the earthquake prevention and emergency planning of any city. Furthermore, the simulation will also provide detailed information on the impact of the chosen scenario earthquakes for the different districts or sectors of the Orihuela municipality and the Hospital de La Vega Baja also in the same municipality.

2 METHODOLOGY

The methodology used has followed these steps:

- a) The researchers from the University of Alicante (UA) had a meeting with the Valencian Cartographic Institute, the provincial council of Alicante, Valencia and Castellón and the Security and Emergency Response Valencian Agency. The meeting was used as a marketing and replication forum by explaining the main goal of TURNkey platform and to generate interest of the demonstration. All the agencies showed their interest so they decided to buy six

RS4D TURNkey sensors which can be integrated in the platform once installed and they encouraged us to fulfill an installation in some municipality of Alicante to be used as a proof of concept for the rest of the municipalities of the region.

- b) Additionally, the UA researchers contacted the local city council of Orihuela. Orihuela is one of the largest and most populated municipalities of the Alicante province as well as a city with a large historical heritage to be protected. Besides, it is located in the most active zone of the Alicante province being affected by the historical 1829 Torrevieja earthquake. The municipality also showed interest in hosting the demonstration by facilitating a venue for the conferences and by allowing us to install TURNkey instruments in historical buildings and an essential facilities such as the Hospital de la Vega Baja. Although the integration of these sensors into the platform will not be completed before the end of the project due to time constraints, it will allow future testing in Alicante and will be a good marketing tool.
- c) Therefore, the workshop was dedicated to demonstrate the benefits of the TURNkey platform to improve the seismic resilience of the city. The event was condensed in three days: Day 1 to engage Spanish stakeholders through Spanish conference related to the seismic risk management in general, and Day 2 to show Spanish stakeholder the TURNkey project and carry out a demonstration of the TURNkey platform using specific information (including the hospital); Day 3 to engage Spanish and International Stakeholder in a specific workshop related with TURNkey installation, data compilation and use.

3 DEMONSTRATION OF THE TURNKEY PLATFORM

3.1 The Alicante province

The Alicante province is located south-east of Spain and south of the Valencia region. It is divided in 144 municipalities. The three municipalities with a large geographical extension and number of inhabitants are the municipality of Alicante (201.27 km² and 337500 inhabitants approx.), the municipality of Elche (326.07km² and 230400 inhabitants approx.) and the municipality of Orihuela (384 km² and 102100 inhabitants) as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. (Left) Administrative division of Spain in provinces. The region of Valencia is formed by the three provinces with light-brown colour (Castellon to the north, Valencia in the middle and Alicante to the south). (Right) Administrative division of the Alicante province in municipalities. There is a total of 144 municipalities.

The Iberian Peninsula shows a low to moderate seismicity in the world context with frequent earthquakes of moment magnitude (M_w) generally smaller than 5.5. However, historically, large damaging earthquakes have occurred with epicentral macroseismic intensity IX-X on the EMS-98 scale, as those of 1829 Torrevieja (Alicante) and 1884 Arenas del Rey (Granada). Both earthquakes caused the collapse of many buildings and a high number of human losses (Vidal, 1986).

3.2 Platform installation and setting up

The platform installation relies on the instrumentation, low-cost RS4D sensors developed during the project, the scientific engine and the cloud-based graphical user interface.

The seismic sensors collect and process the seismic data through the seismic monitoring platform SeisComp3. The resultant dynamic input data are then sent to the scientific engine at request through two application programming interfaces (APIs), namely QuakeLink (for inventory data and dynamic event data, including location, magnitude, instrument arrival data, and Did-You-Feel-It or DYFI felt reports) and common acquisition protocol server (CAPS) for seismic instrument recordings and the corresponding peak intensity measure, e.g., peak ground acceleration (PGA). If non-seismic instrument recordings are also installed then other parameters, as for example radon data, are collected.

The scientific engine is composed of various internal processes, such as the earthquake early warning (EEW) process, the rapid response to earthquake (RRE) process, the operational earthquake forecasting (OEF) process and event listener process. These processes can be triggered to perform the desired analysis and the mutual communication (e.g., notify, read and write) between these processes and the TURNkey database (DB).

The graphical user interface (GUI) facilitates and evaluates risk management in real-time and in various risk scenarios. On one hand, the GUI visualizes the results sent by the scientific engine at both regional (i.e., map) and local (e.g., building-specific information) levels and constantly refreshes the visualizations if results are updated.

3.2.1 Configuration and setting up of the low cost TURNkey sensors

The University of Alicante is currently developing a full sensor setup in the Valencia region. Therefore, the University of Alicante has bought 16 RS4D TURNkey sensors which are going to be used for building monitoring. The first 8 sensors were bought before the demonstration of the platform, as a marketing strategy to engage the municipality of Orihuela. The last 8 sensors were bought after the demonstration once the municipality of Orihuela was chosen for a full TURNkey platform installation as a part of the replication strategy. Additionally, Valencian Cartographic Institute with the cooperation of the Diputación de Alicante, Valencia and Castellón has also acquired 6 RS4D TURNkey sensors to be donated to the ongoing TURNkey platform installation. The TURNkey station deployment consists of structural health monitoring. Due to data protection constraints and to enable secure data transfer from the Hospital de la Vega Baja to the University of Alicante five routers were installed. In addition, existing sensors in the regional seismic network along with the national seismic networks, will be connected in the future.

Table 1 presents the number of sensors and their position within the instrumented buildings in the municipality of Orihuela. The locations of the proposed buildings are as shown in Figure 3.

Table 1. Proposed buildings to install RS4D TURNkey sensors

Building	Number of sensors	Sensor position
Hospital Vega Baja, Orihuela	5	top floor (4)
		ground floor (1)
Aula de Cultura Fundación (CAM), Orihuela	3	top floor (2)
		ground floor (1)
Palacio Arneva, Orihuela	3	top floor (2)
		ground floor (1)
Colegio Santo Domingo, Orihuela	5	top floor (4)
		ground floor (1)
Public residential with different typologies	6	To be specified later

Figure 3. Overview of proposed buildings to install RS4D TURNkey sensors in the municipality of Orihuela, shown in a map (the location of public residential buildings will be specified later).

3.2.2 Setup of the scientific engines

3.2.2.1 Parameters

The parameter setup for Alicante demo follows the description given in Deliverable 6.6, Chapter 3.

3.2.2.2 Hazard data

3.2.2.2.1 Seismic zonation map

A seismic zonation map is useful for hazard reduction such as earthquake-resistant design of structures, risk analysis, land-use planning and other applications. Spain is a country with low to moderate seismic hazard when compared to other European countries such as Italy or Greece. However, the country has suffered several damaging earthquakes in the past, the most important of which are the 1829 Torrevieja earthquake with a maximum intensity IX-X and Mw 6.6, and the 1884

Arenas del Rey earthquake with a maximum intensity IX-X and Mw 6.5 (Mezcua et al., 2004). Therefore, the first national seismic building design code using a probabilistic seismic hazard map was approved in 1994. Later, the code's seismic hazard map was updated after the damaging earthquakes that occurred in the south-east of Spain, namely the 1999 Mula earthquake, the 2002 Bullas earthquake, the 2005 La Peca earthquake, and the 2011 Lorca earthquake. Those events were characterised by a moment magnitudes ranging from 4.7 to 5.2.

The new seismic hazard map (IGN-UPM Working Group, 2013) was the result of a project carried out collaboratively by the National Geographic Institute (IGN) and the Earthquake Engineering Research Group of the Technical University of Madrid (UPM), which used the seismic zonation map provide by (IGME, 2015). This zonation map (Figure 4) was also recently used by (Kharazian et al., 2021) to compute risk-targeted hazard maps for Spain.

Figure 4. Seismic zonation map for Alicante province

3.2.2.2.2 V_{S30} data

The V_{S30} data (defined as the average seismic shear-wave velocity from the surface to a depth of 30 m) are used to classify ground types in Eurocode 8 (EN-1998, 2005), which is then used to account for the influence of local ground conditions on seismic action. V_{S30} is also used in international standards (e.g., (ASCE, 2017)) for site classification and used as a proxy for site amplification in the ground motion prediction models (Lanzano, et al., 2019).

A global V_{S30} map for the whole province of Alicante has been compiled using the USGS global V_{S30} map and previous V_{S30} local studies in the province of Alicante (Figure 5).

3.2.2.2.3 Ground Motion Prediction Equations

The last seismic hazard and risk studies carried out for Spain (IGN-UPM Working Group, 2013) (IGN-UPM Working Group, 2013; Kharazian et al., 2021) indicated that there are two main ground motion prediction equations (GMPE) valid for the Alicante province if the earthquakes are shallow.

The GMPE are: (Akkar & Bommer, 2010)) weighted 0.7, and (Cauzzi & Faccioli, 2008) weighted 0.3.

Figure 5. The synthetic V_{S30} map for Alicante province

3.2.2.3 Exposure data

Exposure of people and properties to earthquake is a key component in seismic risk estimation. The province of Alicante is divided administratively into 140 municipalities with a total of 332780 buildings and 1165695 dwellings. The total population is 1830379 inhabitants approximately.

Additionally, the municipality of Orihuela has the main public hospital of the south of the province of Alicante (Hospital de la Vega Baja), a train station and many schools, some of which are considered as cultural heritage.

3.2.2.4 Vulnerability data

To assess the physical and social vulnerabilities of the area of interest, the scientific engine has included libraries of fragility, capacity, vulnerability, damage-to-loss, functionality functions. According to GEM notation, the general building stock in the province of Alicante has been subdivided into 37 taxonomies (Table 2). The vulnerability of each taxonomy is based on the building typology classification that is distributed into six vulnerability classes (A to F) from most vulnerable to least vulnerable typologies and it is measured by using a vulnerability index (V) which varies from the least vulnerable to the most vulnerable between 0 to 1. The value takes into account not only the

structural typology features but also other factors that influence the building performance (for example, construction quality, plan, and vertical irregularities, number of floor, etc.).

Table 2. Taxonomies for the general building stock in the Alicante province

Taxonomy	N. of buildings	N. of Dwellings	Population	Vuln. Index (V)
MUR-STRUB/LWAL-DUN/H:1	3919	3569	6588	0.853
MUR-STRUB/LWAL-DUN/H:2	5907	6053	10550	0.853
MUR-STDRE/LWAL-DUN/H:1	8186	7651	14655	0.658
MUR-STDRE/LWAL-DUN/H:2	11776	12302	21587	0.658
MUR-CL99/LWAL-DUN/H:1	11339	10779	20109	0.674
MUR-CL99/LWAL-DUN/H:2	12134	12833	22858	0.674
MUR-CL99/LWAL-DUN/H:3-5	7604	11850	21298	0.714
MUR-CL99/LWAL-DUN/H:5+	318	2247	3812	0.754
MUR/LWAL-DUN/H:1	27719	26877	46448	0.596
MUR/LWAL-DUN/H:2	24473	28626	50184	0.596
MUR/LWAL-DUN/H:3-5	14603	66455	126841	0.636
MUR/LWAL-DUN/H:5+	6587	107093	195849	0.676
CR/LFM-DUL/H:1	40574	45687	57141	0.562
CR/LFM-DUL/H:2	31732	57304	73922	0.562
CR/LFM-DUL/H:3-5	12492	85581	126031	0.602
CR/LFM-DUL/H:6-8	3786	76982	119458	0.682
CR/LFM-DUL/H:8+	963	48651	76704	0.682
CR/LFM-DUM/H:1	12673	29363	30046	0.402
CR/LFM-DUM/H:2	12371	37708	48546	0.402
CR/LFM-DUM/H:3-5	5879	62649	89257	0.442
CR/LFM-DUM/H:6-8	1988	51950	75295	0.502
CR/LFM-DUM/H:8+	370	24838	42036	0.502
CR/LFM-DUH/H:1	9150	18132	20713	0.242
CR/LFM-DUH/H:2	9861	30428	39462	0.242
CR/LFM-DUH/H:3-5	7814	78913	120566	0.282
CR/LFM-DUH/H:6-8	2152	50004	83534	0.322
CR/LFM-DUH/H:8+	360	25638	42005	0.322
CR/LFINF-DUL/H:1	9596	9511	13805	0.522
CR/LFINF-DUL/H:2	7096	8180	11833	0.522
CR/LFINF-DUL/H:3-5	3190	16374	29377	0.562
CR/LFINF-DUL/H:6-8	1270	20213	37342	0.642
CR/LFINF-DUL/H:8+	462	16027	26444	0.642
CR/LFINF-DUM/H:1	11264	11134	16193	0.482
CR/LFINF-DUM/H:2	8013	9239	13373	0.482
CR/LFINF-DUM/H:3-5	3375	17824	32338	0.522
CR/LFINF-DUM/H:6-8	1362	21331	38433	0.582
CR/LFINF-DUM/H:8+	422	15699	25746	0.582

3.3 Event simulation

The seismic activity of the south of Alicante province is moderate, although some destructive earthquakes have happened with a high recurrence period Figure 6. Some of the most important earthquakes in the Vega Baja of Segura (south of Alicante province) are compiled in Table 3. The epicentral intensity (I_{max}) and the location of the earthquake is also summarised.

Table 3. Main earthquakes occurred in the Vega Baja of Segura

Date	Latitude	Longitude	I_{max}	Location
1048	38° 05' N	-0° 55' W	VIII ($M_w 6.0 \pm 0.8$) *	Orihuela
10-October-1482	38° 05' N	-0° 55' W	VIII ($M_w 6.0 \pm 0.8$) *	Orihuela
15-January-1673	38° 05' N	-0° 55' W	VIII ($M_w 6.0 \pm 0.6$) *	Orihuela
21-March-1829	38° 05' N	-0° 41' W	IX-X ($M_w 6.5 \pm 0.2$) *	Torre Vieja
01-July-1909	38° 00' N	-0° 40' W	VII ($M_w 5.5 \pm 0.6$)	Torre Vieja
10-September-1919	37° 59' N	-0° 52' W	VII-VIII ($M_w 5.3 \pm 0.5$)	S. Miguel de Salinas

* Estimated magnitude

Figure 6. The main earthquakes and corresponding faults in the south of Alicante province

The demonstration of the platform in Alicante has mainly used two events: a repetition of the 1829 Torrevieja earthquake (most destructive scenario) and a magnitude 5.0 with the same epicentre (return period of 100 years). The 1829 Torrevieja earthquake occurred near the city of Torrevieja, Province of Alicante of southern Spain on March 21, 1829. It had an estimated magnitude of 6.5 Mw and a Mercalli intensity of IX (Violent). It severely damaged many cities. The event was named after the city of Torrevieja because it was the largest locality to be affected (Mezcua et al., 2004).

3.3.1 Shakemaps for Alicante province

The platform runs the scenarios of a repetition of the 1829 Torrevieja earthquake (Mw 6.5) and a Mw 5.0 with the same epicenter (Figure 7 and Figure 8), thus allowing the user to compare the affected area with the ranges of PGA. Additionally, Figure 9 and Figure 10 provide the same information in terms of macroseismic intensity. The results are provided in by the platform in less than 15 sec.

Figure 7. Shakemap in terms of PGA for a Mw 6.5 (repetition of the Torrevieja 1829 earthquake)

Figure 8. Shakemap in terms of PGA for a Mw 5.0 earthquake

Figure 9. Shakemap in terms of macroseismic intensity for a Mw 6.5 (Torrevieja 1829 earthquake)

Figure 10. Shakemap in terms of macroseismic intensity for a Mw 5.0 earthquake

3.3.2 Impact for the Alicante province

The platform is also able to provide the user with distribution map corresponding to the homeless population (Figure 11) and the mean damage ratio (Figure 12) related to the above-mentioned scenarios (Mw 6.5 and Mw 5.0). The translation from mean damage ratio to (MDR) mean damage grade is based on Maiwald & Schwarz (2020) as seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Translation of mean damage ratio to mean damage grade

Mean Damage Ratio	Mean Damage Grade	Description
0	D0	No Damage
0.003 -0.05	D1	Negligible to slight damage
0.05 -0.2	D2	Moderate damage
0.2 – 0.6	D3	Substantial to heavy damage
0.6 – 1.0	D4	Very heavy damage
1.0	D5	Destruction

Mw = 5

Mw = 6.5

Figure 11. Distribution map for homeless population for Alicante province

Mw = 5 Mw = 6.5

Figure 12. Mean damage ratio distribution map for Alicante province

3.3.3 Impact for Orihuela municipality

The impact for the General Building Stock in the municipality of Orihuela can be summarised in terms of the affected districts (table or map view) as shown in Figure 13. Besides, the TURNkey platform computes the mean damage ratio for each one of the sectors in the municipality (Figure 14), the amount of debris after the earthquake (Figure 15) or the fatalities in the municipality (Figure 16).

Figure 13. Impact for General Building Stock in the municipality of Orihuela (red means no impact, yellow means moderate impact and red means high impact).

Figure 14. The mean damage ratio for each one of the sectors in the municipality

For the general building, the damage estimates can be checked under the “Impacted Geo Areas” tag as a map, where the colour is defined based on the average mean damage ratio, as shown in Figure 14. Moreover, the results can also be shown as a table, where the average damage state over the geoarea is colour-coded (green-yellow-red corresponds to no damage-partially damaged-damaged states, respectively), as shown in top Figure 13.

Figure 15. The amount of debris after the earthquake

Figure 16. The fatalities in the municipality after the earthquake

3.4 TURNkey Application to Business and Critical Infrastructure Organizations A Hypothetical Hospital Scenario

3.4.1 Description of the Hospital de la Vega Baja

The Hospital VEGA BAJA in Orihuela is assigned to the Health Department nº 21 of the Valencia región. Its address is: Ctra. De Orihuela-Almoradí, km 8 San Bartolomé 03314 Orihuela (Alicante/Alacant) and it belongs to the public health system ruled by Consellería de Sanidad Universal y Salud Publica.

The hospital is located in an independent parcel with a total area of 62641 km² (Figure 17).

Figure 17. The parcel occupied by the Hospital Vega Baja

It consist of two buildings (hospital and cafeteria), circulation roads around the perimeter of the building, car parks for public and private use (workers) and a heliport (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Aerial view of the Hospital Vega Baja and surrounding areas

There are auxiliary buildings on the perimeter of the facilities, an external waste warehouse, an external chemical warehouse, a generator room, and the main electricity intake room of the hospital. The main building is made up of a basement, ground floor, first floor, second floor and roof. The hospital plot is completely independent; there are no other industrial or special risk activities within a 100 m radius.

The total built area of the hospital is 20000 m² approximately (underground, first floor and second floor).

From the observation of the visible details, the building has a reinforced concrete structure, with the exterior cladding made of brick covered with decorative artificial stone and braided concrete slabs and a ceramic vault.

Regarding the main occupancy of the buildings the following data has been compiled (Table 5):

Table 5. Main occupancy of the Hospital Vega Baja

SECOND FLOOR			
Activity	Built Area (m²)	(m²/person)	N° of persons
Hospitalization	3705	0.1	379
FIRST FLOOR			
Activity	Built Area (m²)	(m²/person)	N° of persons
Hospitalization	3705	0.1	379
GROUND FLOOR			
Activity	Built Area (m²)	(m²/person)	N° of persons
Reanimation	165	0.1	17
Surgery	351	0.05	18
Surgery dressing room	77	0.5	39
Intensive Care Unit	649	0.05	65
Major Surgery Unit	310	0.1	31
Delivery Room and Gynecological Urgencies	335	0.1	34
Urgencies	1107	0.1	111
External examination rooms	342	0.1	34
Radiology	558	0.1	56
Laboratories	365	0.2	73
Administration	481	0.1	48
Conference Room	160	0.5	80
Resonance	259	0.1	26
Chapel	47	0.5	24
Reception and Hall	301	0.5	150
Waiting Rooms	360	0.5	180
BASEMENT			
Activity	Built Area (m²)	(m²/person)	N° of persons
Mortuary	119	0.1	12
Microbacteria laboratory	107	0.2	21
Sterilization	172	0.1	17
Kitchen	321	0.05	16
Dining Room	146	0.67	97
Pharmacy	246	0.1	25
Dressing Rooms	108	0.5	54
Rehabilitation	48	0.1	5
Gymnasium	176	0.2	15
General Archive	495	0.025	10
Library	89	0.5	45
General Storehouse	928	0.025	23
Maintenance Rooms	832	0.025	21
Offices	1915	0.1	191
Linen	141	0.025	4
Clinic History Archive	150	0.025	4

The hospital operates 24 hours a day, and the occupation will be higher during the day than during the night. The external examination rooms have the maximum occupation (in terms of public and workers) from 08:00 to 15:00. Urgencies usually has the same occupancy all day. The administration, laboratories, etc. used to be occupied from 08:00 to 15:00 although sometimes, if the demand is high, they can be used from 15:00 to 20:00 or even some Saturday or Sunday. Surgery is occupied usually from 08:00 to 15:00, although it can also be used from 15:00 to 20:00. The hospitalization rooms have the maximum occupancy of workers from 08:00 to 15:00 and the maximum occupancy of the public (visitors) from 15:00 to 20:00.

The total population under the influence area of the hospital is around 170516. The total number of workers in the hospital is 1570 approximately. The mean number of people in hospitalization is 215 and the hospital has 319 beds for hospitalization. During the day, it is estimated a total of 1222 workers, 150 patients in emergency department and 900 patients in external examination rooms. During the night, it is estimated a total of 229 workers and 70 patients were in emergency department. During the afternoon, it is estimated a total of 122 workers, 90 patients in emergency department and 70 patients in external examinations rooms.

A hypothetical hospital (merging information from the Hospital de la Vega Baja and other generic sources) scenario was used as the basis to demonstrate the potential application of the TURNkey FWCR platform to a critical infrastructure / business organization. The demonstration took the form of a PowerPoint presentation that explained how the TURNkey FWCR Platform could be applied to a hypothetical hospital to support the development of its business continuity and disaster management plans, to inform earthquake mitigation and preparedness efforts (both physical and operational). The demonstration linked the various stages of business continuity and disaster management planning with the potential outputs generated by the TURNkey FWCR platform before, during and after an earthquake. The PowerPoint slides accompanying the presentation can be found in APPENDIX D

Business continuity and disaster management planning are the processes used by critical infrastructure and business organizations to help them better prepare for, respond to, and recover from a disaster event. Business continuity and disaster management plans reflect the antecedent vulnerability and resilience of an organization to a disaster event through a combination of the impact that the event has on its physical, business and process systems and on the absorptive capacity of the organization to support its recovery following the disaster event (slide 2, APPENDIX D). The workshop presentation sought to match the requirements of business continuity and disaster management plans with the outputs from the TURNkey FWCR platform to demonstrate how the platform could add value to a hypothetical hospital's management team developing (or reviewing) their earthquake preparation, response and recovery actions (slide 3, APPENDIX D). Full details of the business continuity and disaster management planning process can be found in Deliverable D7.7.

Whilst the data used in the presentation was based on an existing hospital within Orihuela, all of the potential application examples were drawn from a range of generic sources (FEMA 396, 2003; FEMA 577, 2007; FEMA 154, 2015; WHO, 2011; Kainsinger et al., 2016a; Kainsinger et al., 2016b; Jacques et al., 2014; Nateghi-Alahi & Izadkhan, 2004; Chand & Loosemore, 2016) and the Vega Baja Orihuela Hospital Self-Protection Plan (Internal document). As such, the example presented at the workshop was entirely hypothetical (synthetic) and did not represent a real hospital. Indeed, the hypothetical hospital scenario presented at the workshop was an extension of the case study hospital

scenario presented in D2.8 modified to reflect the final developments of the TURNkey FWCR platform.

3.4.2 The application of the TURNkey FWCR platform to a hypothetical hospital scenario

The presentation described the application of the TURNkey FWCR platform before, during and after an earthquake from a non-technical stakeholder perspective (slide 2, APPENDIX D). The presentation was divided into 5 sections:

- an introduction to the TURNkey platform and data requirements
- pre-earthquake planning using TURNkey simulations
- earthquake response using TURNkey's early warning and rapid response facilities
- earthquake recovery using TURNkey's damage estimates and eye-witness reporting
- aftershock forecasts and overall integration

3.4.2.1 Use of the TURNkey FWCR platform before an earthquake

The TURNkey FWCR platform has the ability to simulate the potential impact of an earthquake on a region and, if appropriate data is entered into the platform, on the critical infrastructure/buildings in that region. The data required by the TURNkey FWCR platform includes the: number and location of the organization's built assets; building location, classification, description, taxonomy, size and occupancy type; cost data; vulnerability index and shear wave velocity (slide 7, APPENDIX D). Whilst most of this data should be readily available to larger critical infrastructure and business organizations, some of the data may need to be generated by internal staff or external consultants.

In addition to built asset data the TURNkey FWCR platform also needs operational and disaster management data including occupancy levels at different times of the day; contact details of key employees and external agencies/stakeholders that would be involved in responding to an earthquake; details of standard operating procedures that would be activated during an earthquake; and automated messages that could be sent out after an earthquake (slide 8, APPENDIX D). The amount of operational information entered into the system depends upon the degree to which the TURNkey FWCR platform is integrated into the organization's business continuity and disaster management processes.

Once the hospital's data has been entered into the TURNkey FWCR platform the hospital can check and validate its data through the user interface (slides 9 and 10, APPENDIX D). The TURNkey FWCR platform can simulate the potential impact (PGA and damage estimates) of a range of earthquakes across a region (slide 12, APPENDIX D) and the hospital can obtain a view of its potential risk. In this scenario, the hospital is located in a medium to high impact region (slide 13, APPENDIX D) and is expected to be severely impacted by the earthquake (slides 14), experiencing human losses and only able to provide very limited functionality immediately after the earthquake (slide 15, APPENDIX D). This level of information is useful to both the hospital business continuity and disaster management planning team as they prepare their plans, and to the wider healthcare infrastructure planning team as they seek to understand the medical resources that could be available to the local community after an earthquake.

Multiple simulations can be run that reflect a range of earthquake magnitudes (slide 16, APPENDIX D) and a range of mitigation actions (slide 17, APPENDIX D) can be evaluated for the different

impact profiles. If the potential impact is deemed to be acceptable or manageable then the hospital could evaluate the potential of the TURNkey FWCR platform to form part of its business continuity and disaster management plans, including its use in evaluating the need for physical mitigation actions, such as the seismic rehabilitation of vulnerable structures; its integration into emergency management plans; the linking of an early warning alert to the safe shutdown of critical systems; coordination of its communication and recovery plans; and the rapid activation of backup facilities and workarounds.. Although the TURNkey FWCR platform does not provide the level of detail to support full seismic rehabilitation calculations it can give an estimate of the potential changes in the damage states and losses associated with different rehabilitation strategies (slides 18, 19 and 20, APPENDIX D). This information could help the hospital's senior management assess the potential benefits of different refurbishment strategies. In addition to mitigation options for the hospital's physical assets, mitigation options would also include potential changes to non-structural systems to reduce the impact of damage to the systems on the hospital's operational vulnerabilities.

If the potential impact is deemed to be acceptable or manageable then the hospital could evaluate the potential of the TURNkey FWCR platform to form part of its business continuity and disaster management plans, including its use in evaluating the need for physical mitigation actions, such as the seismic rehabilitation of vulnerable structures; its integration into emergency management plans; the linking of an early warning alert to the safe shutdown of critical systems; coordination of its communication and recovery plans; and the rapid activation of backup facilities and workarounds.

3.4.2.2 Use of the TURNkey FWCR platform during an earthquake

The TURNkey FWCR platform has the ability to issue an earthquake early warning when an earthquake or aftershock is detected where the warning time is depending on the distance to the earthquake source: as larger the distance as more warning time. If the TURNkey FWCR platform is integrated into the hospital's disaster management and business continuity plans, these warnings provide the potential to reduce casualties amongst the hospital staff, patients and visitors and to improve the coordination and response of the hospital's staff to the earthquake (slide 22, APPENDIX D). If the expected intensity of the detected earthquake is forecasted to exceed a pre-set warning alert threshold an alert will be issued on the TURNkey FWCR platform dashboard (slide 23, APPENDIX D). Whilst the TURNkey FWCR platform can issue an alert directly to the hospital, in the current operational model it is anticipated that the alert will be moderated through a responsible person in the control room (slide 5, APPENDIX D).

On receiving an early warning alert, the hospital can initiate immediate action to reduce the potential impact of the earthquake. If the hospital integrates the early warning system into its internal alarm system it can sound a warning alarm across its built assets advising its staff, patients and visitors to drop, cover, hold on; and if there is sufficient time, to initiate action to protect vulnerable patients and critical services. The hospital can also send pre-written communications to its emergency response and recovery teams advising them that an earthquake has occurred and initiating response protocols (slides 24 and 25, APPENDIX D). The hospital can also issue general pre-written messages to key contacts and the public via social media, advising them on the situation and the potential impact of the earthquake on the hospital's functionality (slide 26, APPENDIX D).

3.4.2.3 Use of the TURNkey FWCR platform after an earthquake

When an earthquake is detected, the TURNkey FWCR platform will provide a very early estimate of the earthquake's intensity (PGA) and expected damage state zones for the impacted region (slide 28, APPENDIX D). The hospital can compare this information with previously run simulations to obtain an early estimate of the potential damage state of their buildings and the potential impact that this could have on service delivery. This will allow the hospital to better manage its response to the immediate impact of the earthquake by reviewing and modifying priorities for its on-site intervention teams and by initiating departmental level (critical service level) inspection, repair and recovery plans. It will also allow the hospital's senior management to communicate their expected level of functional performance with civil protection and the wider regional health sector (slide 29, APPENDIX D). If an appropriate pre-existing simulation does not exist, the hospital can generate a new simulation based upon the actual earthquake characteristics generated by the TURNkey FWCR platform's early estimates.

The TURNkey FWCR platform will continuously monitor seismic activity and integrate this with real-time eye-witness reporting to generate new ShakeMaps and damage estimates. Eye-witness observation is collected through the TURNkey app or entered directly into the TURNkey FWCR platform dashboard. The eye-witness reporting function will allow the hospital's 'authorized' personnel (e.g., security, maintenance, facilities management staff etc.) to provide specific details on the damage state and level of functional performance of individual buildings, or parts of buildings, and on the level of casualties (slide 32, APPENDIX D). Eye-witness reports are validated by the platform operator before being uploaded to the scientific engine (slide 33, APPENDIX D). The updated damage state and functional performance information will again allow the hospital to better manage its immediate response to the earthquake and allow it to focus its resources on the most critical areas to return to a level of functional performance as quickly as possible. The information will also be of use to the wider healthcare sector as it seeks to manage the wider response to regional casualties.

As the hospital's response moves from a disaster management role to a business recovery role, the TURNkey FWCR platform can be used in a coordinating role to monitor the progress of response and recovery activities (slide 32, APPENDIX D) and early warning role in the case of aftershocks. The TURNkey FWCR platform continuously monitors seismic activity to detect potential aftershocks. The TURNkey FWCR platform can provide regular updates on the change in seismic activity which can potentially provide an operational earthquake forecast of an impending aftershock (slide 33, APPENDIX D). Although the level of uncertainty associated with such forecasts is high, the hospital's management could use this information to suspend recovery activity in vulnerable areas for the duration of a raised level of alert. If an aftershock is detected, the TURNkey FWCR platform will issue an alert along with a request for any users of the app (e.g., the hospital's response teams) that are in the impacted area to confirm that they are safe once the aftershock has passed (slide 34, APPENDIX D). If an "I'm safe" response isn't received the hospital's management can initiate action to confirm the status of the user. This facility again allows the hospital's management to better manage the recovery process.

Whilst the presentation was not exhaustive in its potential application of the TURNkey FWCR platform to a hospital scenario (e.g., it didn't go into specific operational details), it did demonstrate the potential value of the TURNkey FWCR platform as a decision support tool that the hospital's senior management could use to help them better understand their vulnerabilities to an earthquake

and develop emergency response and recovery plans to manage the immediate impact and short-term recovery of the hospital following an earthquake. Taken together, this would allow the hospital to develop more effective disaster management and business continuity plans. Finally, as the hospital's use of the TURNkey FWCR platform is directly linked to the region/city's use of the platform it is possible for the hospital's business continuity and disaster management plans to be tested as part of integrated training exercises run at the regional level. This will provide hospital senior managers with the ability to test and adjust their plans to reflect the results of simulated earthquake response scenarios.

4 MAIN DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION FROM THE STAKEHOLDERS

4.1.1 Spanish and International Stakeholders

Regarding the Spanish stakeholders attending the demonstration of the platform (in total 50), we can point out that 25 of them belonged to the municipalities of the Alicante province, 6 of them belonged to rapid response teams (firefighters, red cross, military emergency unit, police), one of them belonged to the emergency team of the Alicante international airport and 18 of them belonged to companies or students related to the disaster management. On the other hand, regarding the international stakeholders, due to travel restrictions, only two stakeholders from Iceland and one from Japan attended face to face the demonstration. Additionally, online streaming of the whole workshop was broadcasted, allowing partners and interested international stakeholders to participate in the demonstration.

4.1.2 Results from the survey of opinion

A SWOT analysis questionnaire (APPENDIX C) was translated into Spanish and sent to the Spanish stakeholders to overview their opinion regarding the TURNkey platform. 80% of the answer are from governmental organizations, 10% from rapid response teams, and 10% from critical infrastructure emergencies. The main results are:

4.1.2.1 Governance and management aspect to enhance urban resilience

- a) The Spanish stakeholders agree with the statement that TURNkey will contribute effectively to the governance and management when using it for planning and organizing, use of current and future risk scenarios, and financial capacity (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Questionnaire results related to TURNkey contributions (strengths and weaknesses) in governance and management

b) The Spanish stakeholder agree with the statement that the external factors such as the use of current and future risk scenarios and the planning and organizing are an opportunity which it will enable TURNkey's uptake; however, the financial capacity can be a weakness (Figure 20).

- **An opportunity: external factors enable TURNkey's uptake**
- **A threat: external factors limit TURNkey's uptake** ■ **Neither a strength nor a weakness**

Figure 20. Questionnaire results related to TURNkey contributions (opportunities and threats) in governance and management

4.1.2.2 Planning and design aspect to reduce urban exposure and vulnerability

a) They agree that one of the TURNkey strengths is the ability to contribute to Urban development effectively, Natural buffers, Societal capacity, Institutional capacity and infrastructure (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Questionnaire results related to TURNkey contributions (strengths and weaknesses) in the five aspects of planning and design

b) They also agree that the external factors are an opportunity: external factors enable TURNkey's uptake (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Questionnaire results related to TURNkey contributions (opportunities and threats) in the five aspects of planning and design

4.1.2.3 Disaster preparedness aspect for response and recovery

a) They also agree with the statement that TURNkey will effectively contribute to effective disaster response and expedite recovery and build back better (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Questionnaire results related to TURNkey contributions (strengths and weaknesses) in the aspects of disaster preparedness

b) They also agree with the statement that external factors are an opportunity: external factors enable TURNkey's uptake (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Questionnaire results related to TURNkey contributions (opportunities and threats) in the aspects of disaster preparedness.

5 CONCLUSIONS

To demonstrate the benefits of the TURNkey platform and encourage uptake of tools and measures, a demo concerning its use has been developed for the Alicante province, the municipality of Orihuela and a hypothetical hospital based on the Hospital de la Vega Baja.

Orihuela (Alicante province, Spain) hosted the TURNkey final meeting (from 25 April to 28 April 2022). The final project event included a two-and-a-half-day workshop where the demonstration of the TURNkey platform, focused on the province of Alicante, was carried out. The workshop took place in the Auditorio de La Lonja and it brought together stakeholders from the municipalities of the Alicante province, rapid response teams from the firefighters, red cross, police, emergency military unit, and the policy makers of the regional and national civil protection agencies. The workshop was also an opportunity to transfer the knowledge from the TURNkey scientist with the society.

The first day was dedicated to enhancing the seismic risk knowledge to the Spanish stakeholders while the second and third days were about the TURNkey project. Several partners of the TURNkey consortium presented the activities carried out within the project and their achievements. Using the TURNkey platform, a simulation of the occurrence of a damaging earthquake in the municipality of Orihuela was also performed. The purpose of the simulation was to show representatives of the municipalities and emergency response how the TURNkey platform works and how the tool can be used to plan and manage the emergency in case of a seismic event. The last day was used to summarise the project status to the TURNkey partners and think over future developments.

The presentations that TURNkey partners gave during the workshop are available in the tab [New&Events](#) on the TURNkey website.

Leaflets, posters, on-site demonstrations of the RS4D sensors, videos of the presentations were prepared and shared with the stakeholders during the workshop as a marketing strategy. Additionally, politicians, the civil protection and stakeholders were actively engaged during the organization of the demo.

Finally, as a main conclusion, Iceland, Greece and Spain (Orihuela municipality) were chosen as the places to carry out the full TURNkey platform installation. Although the platform is still in beta version and it can not be delivered as a commercial, scientific or educational tool, these installations

will serve as an example for the rest of testbeds and other countries as a part of the developed replication strategy. Appendix E shows the expression of interest of the municipality of Orihuela as a main result of the marketing and replication strategy used during the demonstration.

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APPENDIX A

TURNkey leaflets

Application (TURNkey Platform)

TURNkey Consortium

TURNkey Kick-Off Meeting, 13-14 June 2019, Oslo, Norway.

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TURNkey platform

Coordinator
NORSAR

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- INFP
- gempa
- Nutracker Research
- Siminn
- University of Patras
- yet:it moves!
- UCL
- BEIR 30 GROUP

TURNkey

Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821046.

Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF)

The OEF first requests the recent earthquake event catalogue (a strong mainshock-aftershock sequence) to estimate the short-term seismicity. The estimated daily probability of exceeding PGA level 0.005g based on the background and time-dependent seismicity data are presented in the platform. The increased probability of strong shaking in area of interest is computed based on these two maps. For comparison purpose, the OEF results based on strong and weak mainshock-aftershock sequences are also presented below.

Earthquake Early Warning (EEW)

The EEW alert of events (for both mainshock and aftershocks) will appear on the TURNkey platform if the scientific engine sends out relevant notification. The end-user can check the most affected area to have a first estimate of the earthquake impact. For an earthquake with potential damaging impact, shakemaps of PGA and macroseismic intensity will be made available timely.

Rapid Response to Earthquake (RRE)

With the streaming instrumental data and smart-phone data, the shakemaps of PGA and macroseismic intensity are updated consequently. For the general buildings, the risk and loss estimation can be checked under the 'Impacted Geo Areas' tag as a map, where the colour is defined based on the mean damage ratio. Moreover, the results can also be shown as a table, where the average damage state over the geoaera is color-coded (green-yellow-red corresponds to no damage-partially damaged-damaged states, respectively). The user can submit eyewitness report through either the platform or the TURNkey app.

Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF)

TURNkey Consortium

TURNkey Kick-Off Meeting, 13-14 June 2019, Oslo, Norway.

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Operational Earthquake Forecasting

Objectives and benefits

Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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- INFP
- gempa
- Nutracker Research
- Síminn
- University of Patras
- BETA BI GROUP
- yet:moves!
- UCL
- Geomatics Engineering Center
- Geomatics Engineering Center
- Geomatics Engineering Center

Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF)

Operational earthquake forecasting systems are a collection of procedures for gathering and disseminating authoritative information about the time dependence of seismic hazards to help communities prepare for earthquake events. The TURNkey project will utilise the developed platform to collate and manage all long-term earthquake-hazard related information, and through the multi-sensor-based earthquake information system, monitor short-term changes to this information. Critical to this task is the need to develop criteria that validate any observed changes and governs the dissemination of subsequent warnings. With regard to the latter, it is important that any time-dependent hazard changes are transmitted in an understandable and useful format to end-users. A color-based alert code (e.g. red, amber and green), whose color depends on the OEF forecasting will improve the employee safety, reduce disruption to business, and prevent cascading hazard events.

TURNkey proposal

The ETAS (Epidemic-Type Aftershock Sequences) seismicity model, has been implemented within the TURNkey platform. The ETAS model provides spatial earthquake occurrence rates for magnitudes larger than a defined threshold for a specific forecasting time interval. The short-term forecasting time interval can range from hours to weeks. Reasenberg and Jones (R&J) model is a well-known and commonly-used statistical model to forecast the aftershock rate following a mainshock.

Radon anomalies can start before the occurrence of the earthquake and can last days, weeks, or months after the event. TURNkey platform correlates the daily seismic change in the seismic activity rate over a threshold magnitude with the radon gas emissions (or corresponding anomalies). The results from the model can be expressed as the increment in the percentage of the daily seismic activity rate over the background seismicity for a threshold magnitude, which can be later used to compute short-term probabilistic seismic hazard analysis. The goal of any OEF is to provide effective parameters that can be employed to recommend mitigation actions. These mitigation actions can be better attributed to short-term time-dependent loss than hazard estimates, because the obtained losses can be used to conduct a simple cost-benefit analysis (or a more sophisticated type of decision making) to assess in which cases the proposed actions are favourable.

TURNkey Final Outcomes

OEF maps show the seismic hazard in the region, either as a background hazard map (regular), as a time-dependent hazard map (forecast of hazard) or as time-dependent probability gain (forecast, ratio between the two other maps). Below, some result examples are shown for TB-4: Patras, Greece.

TURNkey's Geographical European Testbeds

Earthquake Early Warning (EEW)

TURNkey Consortium

TURNkey Kick-Off Meeting, 13-14 June 2019, Oslo, Norway.

Follow us

www.earthquake-turnkey.eu

T For any information and clarifications about the TURNkey project, please write to: info@earthquake-turnkey.eu

Earthquake Early Warning

Objectives and benefits

Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821046.

Coordinator
NORSAR

Participants

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- Strathclyde Glasgow
- Universitat d'Alacant
- UNIVERSITÀ DEL SAURO
- INFP
- gempa
- Nutracker Research
- Siminn
- CSEM EMSC
- Palau de les Illes Balears
- University of Wuppertal
- a.r.u.
- UCL
- yet:tmoves!
- BETA 80 GROUP
- UNIVERSITY OF PATRAS

Earthquake Early Warning (EEW)

Earthquake Early Warning (EEW) is a relatively new strategy for reducing disaster risk and increasing resilience to seismic hazard in urban settings. EEW systems provide real-time information about ongoing earthquakes, enabling individuals, communities, governments, businesses and others located at a distance to take timely action to reduce the probability of harm or loss before the earthquake-induced ground shaking reaches them. EEW systems are primarily based on two concepts that enable alerts to be sent ahead of the occurrence of earthquake-induced ground shaking at target locations (on the order of seconds to minutes): (1) information travels faster than seismic (i.e., mechanical) waves; and (2) most of the energy of an earthquake is carried by the S- and surface waves, which arrive after the faster, lower amplitude P-waves. This warning time, although short, can reduce the impacts of an earthquake on many sectors of society.

TURNkey proposal

EMSC has developed a system call CsLoc (Crowdseeded Seismic Location) (Steed et al., 2019) for the detection of felt earthquakes via crowdsourcing, which is capable determine fast and reliable seismic locations with only few seismic stations. CsLoc methodology has been significantly improved since the start of the TURNkey project over three main aspects. First, an algorithm to detect multiple crowd-sourced detections generated by the same event has been implemented. Second, EQN detections have been added and third, the computation of the magnitude has been implemented. 362 seismic stations have been added to collect picks-arrival times and amplitudes to increase our seismic network coverage.

TURNkey Final Outcomes

EEW maps are a kind of shake map and show a very quick estimate of shaking levels, based on a limited number of stations. The number of stations used for the map increases as time progresses. There are three instances in time when EEW maps are produced: Level 1, 2 and 3 EEW maps. A Level 1 map is produced as soon as possible, Level 2 at 20% of time span in which earthquake parameters are refined and Level 3 is the final EEW map. Each higher Level map includes data from an increasing number of stations.

Figure reference:
Cremen, G. and Galasso, C., 2020. Earthquake early warning: Recent advances and perspectives. Earth-Science Reviews, 205, p.103184.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2020.103184>

TURNkey's Geographical European Testbeds

Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE)

TURNkey Consortium

TURNkey Kick-Off Meeting, 13-14 June 2019, Oslo, Norway.

Follow us

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T For any information and clarifications about the TURNkey project, please write to: info@earthquake-turnkey.eu

Coordinator

NORSAR

Participants

Rapid Response to Earthquakes

Objectives and benefits

TURNkey

Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821046.

Rapid Response to Earthquake (RRE)

In a Rapid Response to Earthquake context, the main objective pertains to the accurate estimation of the extent and location of incurred losses, within the shortest time possible following the earthquake event. Therefore, many automated tools and systems for damage and loss estimation have been developed and implemented worldwide. RRE that can capture and interrogate information received from those responding to an earthquake event to improve their post-event critical response planning to reflect the real situation on the ground. This would include greater awareness of the specific danger to first responders, including early notification of aftershocks.

TURNkey proposal

When an earthquake is detected, the magnitude and the location of the hypocenter are estimated. A Ground Motion Model (GMM), also called Ground Motion Prediction Equation (GMPE), is then applied in order to estimate ground-motion parameters around the hypocenter (each GMM having specific validity criteria such as magnitude range, fault mechanism and dimension, distance to the source, geodynamical context). The observations recorded during the event (i.e., ground-motion measurements and macroseismic intensities when available) are collected, sometimes corrected by site amplification factors (in order to adjust the measurements from soil conditions to rock conditions) and used to update the distribution of the ground-motion field. The latter result is called a shake-map, which is an estimate of the ground motion usually in the form of intensity measures (IMs) such as PGA (Peak Ground Acceleration), SA (Spectral Acceleration), PGV (Peak Ground Velocity) or macroseismic intensity.

TURNkey Final Outcomes

RRE maps are shake maps and show the level of shaking after an earthquake. The level can be expressed as PGA or as intensity (EMS-98). The levels of shaking for all coordinates on a grid are calculated by the engine, for the low best and high estimates. TURNkey platform provides continuously updated information about:

- Location and extent of damage to buildings, strategic infrastructure and road networks.
- Number and location of infrastructure units still operational

TURNkey's Geographical European Testbeds

TB-2: Pyrenees Mountain Range France

TB-3: Húsavík and Hveragerði Iceland

APPENDIX B

Workshop Pictures

Day 1 (25th, April 2022)

Figure B 1. Opening the workshop

Figure B 2. Seismic risk in the municipality of Orihuela (Sergio Molina Palacios -UA)

Figure B 3. The Valencian Community seismic network (Jose Delgado Marchall, Head of the Valencia Region Seismic Network)

Figure B 4. The seismic risk municipality emergency plans (Maria José Crespo – Head of the regional emergency agency)

Figure B 5. Emergency management. The case of Lorca (Maria Sofía González López) (Civil protection of Murcia region)

Figure B 6. Protection and prevention of built heritage (Yolanda Spairani Berrio- UA - architect working of historical heritage)

Figure B 7. Protection and prevention of built heritage (Yolanda Spairani Berrio- UA - architect working of historical heritage)

Figure B 8. Evaluation of urban seismic vulnerability based on construction typologies and urban layout of the building (Sandra Martínez Cuevas - UPM -architect working on vulnerability)

Figure B 9. Seismic vulnerability of historical heritage in Valencia (Arianna Guardiola Villora - UPV - architect working on vulnerability)

Day 2 (26th, April 2022)

Figure B 10. TURNkey Project presentation (Johannes, NOR)

Figure B 11. Using Operational Earthquake Forecasting within TURNkey (Alireza, UStr)

Figure B 12. Using Earthquake Early Warning and rapid ground motion estimation within TURNkey (Gemma, UCL)

Figure B 13. Vulnerability and Rapid Loss Prediction Updating within TURNkey (Pierre, BRGM)

Figure B 14. TURNkey platform general presentation (Abdelghani/Alberto, NOR/B80)

Figure B 15. Experiences from Testbeds (Benedikt, UIce)

Figure B 16. Demonstration of the TURNkey platform (Abdelghani/Alberto, NOR/B80)

Figure B 17. Application to Alicante (The Municipalities) (Alberto, B80)

Figure B 18. TURNkey Application to Business and Critical Infrastructure Organizations: A Hypothetical Hospital Scenario (Keith, ARU)

Day 3 (27th, April 2022)

Figure B 19. Civil protection and first responders research (Celia, NTC)

Figure B 20. Use cases for businesses and critical infrastructures (Femke, ARU)

Figure B 21. Stakeholders workshop (NOR/B80/GMP)

Figure B 22. Management updates / Final Reporting (Ivan, NOR)

Figure B 23. Input from the EC (Project Officer)

Figure B 24. Dissemination, Exploitation, and potential routes to market

Figure B 25. General Assembly

Day 4 (28th, April 2022)

Figure B 26. Installation of the platform in the Testbeds (NOR, B80, GMP, TB leaders)

APPENDIX C

SWOT Analysis TURNkey

This Appendix corresponds to the quiz that will explore the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) that mark the TURNkey platform. The following figures (from Figure C 1 To Figure C 14) demonstrate the quiz sheets.

SWOT Analysis TURNkey

Thank you for participating in this quiz about the TURNkey platform!

This quiz explores the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT) that mark the TURNkey platform. It asks participants to reflect on if and how community resilience could be improved through TURNkey's earthquake forecasting, simulations, early warning alerts and a rapid response dashboard.

Answers will be treated confidentially.

Introduction

1

Please enter your name (optional)

Figure C 1. Introduction of the quiz sheet

2

Please enter what type of organisation you work for

- Government (e.g., civil protection, local authority, national government)
- First response organisation (e.g., ambulance, police, firebrigade)
- Critical infrastructure (i.e., food, energy, data, space, education, transport, communications, water, health, defence)
- Business organisation
- Other

Figure C 2. Getting information regarding type of the organization

Overview of the quiz

This quiz starts with an overview of community resilience to earthquakes. It focuses on three aspects of community resilience: 1) governance and management, 2) planning and design, and 3) disaster preparedness.

Looking at each one of these three aspects in turn, participants are asked to give their view on TURNkey's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (in the context of that aspect).

An overview of TURNkey's features is provided at the end of the quiz for reference (section 7 onwards).

For each set of questions participants are encouraged to explain their answers: why they believe that something is a strength, a weakness, an opportunity or a threat. Answers can be written in Spanish or English.

Thanks in advance for your time.

Figure C 3. Overview of community resilience to earthquakes

TURNkey's goal is to boost communities' resilience to earthquakes

The purpose of the TURNkey platform is to foster community resilience to earthquakes. Community resilience refers to a community's ability to prevent, prepare for, respond to, and recover from disasters. This quiz focuses on three aspects of community resilience: governance and management, urban planning and design and disaster preparedness.

Figure C 4. Three important aspects of community resilience

Governance and management to enhance urban resilience

The governance and management of urban areas plays an important role in community resilience.

In this section we ask you to consider three important aspects of governance and management: 1) planning and organizing for urban resilience, 2) the use of current and future risk scenarios for hazards and their impacts, and 3) the financial capacity to support urban resilience.

We ask you to reflect on TURNkey's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats for each aspect.

Figure C 5. Three important aspects of governance and management to enhance urban resilience

Governance and Management

Strengths and weaknesses refer to TURNkey's features, i.e., its earthquake simulations, its operational earthquake forecasts, its earthquake early warnings and its dashboard for supporting a rapid response. (See section 7 for an overview of TURNkey's features).

In your view, could TURNkey contribute effectively to the following three aspects of governance and management?

	A strength: TURNkey contributes to this	A weakness: TURNkey does not contribute to this	Neither a strength nor a weakness
Planning and Organizing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Use of current and future risk scenarios	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Financial capacity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure C 6. Questionnaire to assess the contribution of TURNkey to governance and management

Opportunities and threats refer to external factors that enable or limit the effective uptake of the TURNkey platform (such as demand, compatibility with existing systems, legislation, funding).

In your view, how would external factors shape the uptake of the TURNkey platform for governance and management? Please consider each of its three aspects in turn.

	An opportunity : external factors enable TURNkey's uptake	A threat: external factors limit TURNkey's uptake	Neither an opportunity nor a threat
Use of current and future risk scenarios	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Planning and organizing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Financial capacity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure C 7. Questionnaire to assess how external factors shape the uptake of the TURNkey platform

Planning and design to reduce urban exposure and vulnerability

The planning and designing of urban areas to reduce their exposure and vulnerability to hazards plays an important role in community resilience.

In this section we ask you to consider five aspects of planning and design: 1) urban development, 2) natural buffers, 3) societal capacity, 4) infrastructure and 5) institutional capacity.

We ask you to reflect on TURNkey's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats for each aspect.

Figure C 8. Important aspects of planning and design to reduce urban exposure and vulnerability

Planning and design

Strengths and weaknesses refer to TURNkey's internal features, i.e., its earthquake simulations, its operational earthquake forecasts, its earthquake early warnings and its dashboard for supporting a rapid response. (Please see section 7 for an overview).

In your view, could TURNkey contribute effectively to the following five aspects of planning and design for urban resilience?

	A strength: TURNkey contributes to this	A weakness: TURNkey does not contribute to this	Neither a strength nor a weakness
Urban development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Natural buffers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Societal capacity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Institutional capacity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Infrastructure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure C 9. Questionnaire to assess how TURNkey contributes to the five aspects of planning and design

Opportunities and threats refer to external factors that enable or limit the effective uptake of the TURNkey platform (such as demand, compatibility with existing systems, legislation, funding).

In your view, how would external factors shape the uptake of the TURNkey platform for urban planning and design? Please consider each aspect in turn.

	An opportunity : external factors enable TURNkey's uptake	A threat: external factors limit TURNkey's uptake	Neither an opportunity nor a threat
Urban development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Natural buffers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Societal capacity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Institutional capacity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Infrastructure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure C 10. Questionnaire to assess how external factors shape the uptake of the TURNkey platform for urban planning and design

Disaster preparedness for response and recovery

Disaster preparedness for recovery and response plays an important role in community resilience. In this section we ask you to consider two aspects of disaster preparedness: 1) response and 2) recovery

We ask you to reflect on TURNkey's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats for each aspect.

Figure C 11. Important aspects of disaster preparedness for response and recovery

Disaster Preparedness

Strengths and weaknesses refer to TURNkey's internal features, i.e., its earthquake simulations, its operational earthquake forecasts, its earthquake early warnings and its dashboard for supporting a rapid response. (Please see section 7 for an overview).

In your view, could TURNkey contribute effectively to the following two aspects of disaster preparedness for urban resilience?

	A strength: TURNkey contributes to this	A weakness: TURNkey does not contribute to this	Neither a strength nor a weakness
Effective disaster response	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Expedite recovery and build back better	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure C 12. Questionnaire to assess how TURNkey contributes to the aspects of disaster preparedness

Opportunities and threats refer to external factors that enable or limit the effective uptake of the TURNkey platform (such as demand, compatibility with existing systems, legislation, funding).

In your view, how would external factors shape the uptake of the TURNkey platform for disaster preparedness? Please consider each aspect in turn.

	An opportunity : external factors enable TURNkey's uptake	A threat: external factors limit TURNkey's uptake	Neither an opportunity nor a threat
Effective disaster response	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Expedite recovery and build back better	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure C 13. Questionnaire to assess how external factors shape the uptake of the TURNkey platform for disaster preparedness

Thank you very much for your answers! Are there any final comments or questions you would like to share?

Thank You!

Figure C 14. Getting final comments and questions

APPENDIX D

A hypothetical hospital scenario presentation

TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821046

TURNkey Application to Business and Critical Infrastructure Organisations

A Hypothetical Hospital Scenario

1

Introduction

- The application of the TURNkey FWCR Platform to a hypothetical hospital located somewhere in the Alicante province.
- How TURNkey could inform business continuity and disaster management plans.

The diagram illustrates a timeline with three horizontal axes labeled 'Before', 'During', and 'After'. A vertical dashed line marks the 'earthquake' event. To the right, a vertical dashed line marks 'assets at risk'. Above the 'Before' axis, a blue oval labeled 'simulation' has a red arrow pointing to the earthquake. Above the 'During' axis, a blue oval labeled 'early warning' has a red arrow pointing to the earthquake. Below the 'During' axis, a blue oval labeled 'aftershock early warning' has a red arrow pointing to the right. Below the 'After' axis, a blue oval labeled 'short-term rapid response' has a red arrow pointing to the right. Small building icons are placed along the timeline to represent the hospital's state at different points.

2

Entering CI Data into the TURNkey FWCR Platform

- The city/region will have decided to use the TURNkey FWCR Platform.
- Critical infrastructure and business organisations provide the Platform Operator with specific information about their buildings, operational and DMP/BCP procedures
- Building data includes
 - User ID
 - Number of Buildings; Number of Dwellings; to be entered into the Platform
 - For each building
 - Building Name; Building Classification; Building Description; Building Taxonomy (SERA or GEM); Building Location (Longitude and Latitude); Building/Dwelling Area; Occupancy Type
 - Cost per unit area(€); Total Replacement Cost(€); Structural Cost(€); Non-structural Cost(€); Contents Cost(€)
 - Vulnerability Index (0-1 –from regional data)
 - V_{s30}
- Most of the data required should be readily available to business and critical infrastructure organisations but some might need to be generated by consultants.

Entering CI Data into the TURNkey FWCR Platform

- Operational information includes
 - Occupancy Level at different times of day
 - Staffing details, including contact details for key staff
- Business disaster management and continuity information includes
 - Contact details of key individuals that will be responsible for managing the emergency response and recovery operations
 - Head of Emergency; Head of Intervention; Department Heads (and alternates); Intervention Teams; Evacuations Teams etc.
 - Civil protection; emergency responders; critical system suppliers; TV and press contacts
 - Details of standard operating procedures that will be activated during and after an earthquake and safe (offsite) repository for standard documents
 - Evacuation protocols
 - Alternative working procedures
 - Automated messages that can be sent to staff, patients and the public
 - Standard emails
 - Public announcements

Key Contacts for a Hypothetical Hospital

SERVICIO	PERSONA	CONTACTO	RESPUESTA
BCM - TB9	Pérez Pepto	alberto.vezzoso@bctadgroup.it	
BCM - TB9	Bolin Håkan		
BCM - TB9	Delapuentes Concha	alberto.vezzoso@bctadgroup.it	
BCM - TB9	Molina Sergio	sergio.molina@ctioud.es	
BCM - TB9	Mulder Femke	Femke.Mulder@anu.ac.uk	
BCM - TB9	Pomares José María	arthur.fonzarelli@bctadgroup.com	
BCM - TB9	Creppa Conesa Francisco Javier	arthur.fonzarelli@bctadgroup.com	

9

Location of Key Critical Infrastructure and Businesses

- Critical infrastructure and business organisations are shown on a regional map.
 - Three hospitals for this region are shown.

10

Pre-earthquake Planning

Hazard Threat and Impact

TURNkey Simulations

- The TURNkey FWCR can simulate the potential impact of an earthquake on the city / region and its critical infrastructure and buildings

TURNkey Simulations

- The TURNkey FWCR can simulate the potential impact of an earthquake on the city / region and its critical infrastructure and buildings

TURNkey Simulations

- The Hospital disaster care management team can use the simulation to get damage, risk and loss estimates for their buildings

TURNkey Simulations

- The Hospital disaster management team can use the simulation to get damage, risk and loss results for their buildings

TURNkey Simulations

- Multiple simulations can be run for different earthquake scenarios allowing the hospital to assess potential impact

Mw 6.5

Mw 5.0

TURNkey Simulations

- Based on the level of expected damage to the hospital senior managers can use TURNkey data to assess the level of risk and impact on critical systems and functions.
- Unacceptable/unmanageable
 - Seismic rehabilitation plans (full or incremental) to the building structure to reduce vulnerability and increase speed of recovery
 - Structural retrofit
 - Building improvement plans to address non-structural and operational vulnerabilities
 - Secure fixtures and fittings
- Acceptable/manageable
 - Disaster management plans to reduce impact
 - Evacuation procedures (Emergency Management Plans)
 - 'Safe mode' for critical equipment
 - Business continuity plans to manage disruption and increase speed of recovery
 - Communication plans
 - Coordination of recovery plans
 - Back-up facilities (triage area, IT replacement) and work arounds

TURNkey Simulations

- Whilst detailed seismic rehabilitation calculations are outside the scope of the TURNkey FWCR Platform, it can estimate changes in damage state and losses associated with different rehabilitation strategies
 - Existing building

TURNkey Simulations

- Whilst detailed seismic rehabilitation calculations are outside the scope of the TURNkey FWCR Platform, it can estimate changes in damage state and losses associated with different rehabilitation strategies
 - Seismic refurbishment

19

TURNkey Simulations

- Whilst detailed seismic rehabilitation calculations are outside the scope of the TURNkey FWCR Platform, it can estimate changes in damage state and losses associated with different rehabilitation strategies
 - Rebuild to latest code

20

Earthquake Response

Early Warning and Disaster Management Plans

Earthquake Early Warning and Rapid Response

- The TURNkey FWCR Platform's EEW and RRE capabilities can be integrated into disaster management and business continuity plans
- Disaster Management / Emergency Management plans
 - Improved life safety
 - Sound alarm; drop, cover, hold-on; or evacuate if there is time; return lifts to safe location etc.
 - Reduce damage to critical systems
 - Auto shutdown (if appropriate); fail-safe mode etc.
- Business Continuity Plans
 - Improved life safety
 - Advanced warning of risk of aftershocks; early warning of aftershocks; I'm safe function etc.
 - Coordination of response
 - Activation of BCP; convening of command group; early assessment of damage etc.
 - Communication with staff; with patients; with civil protection; with supply chain; the general public etc.
- Provide training scenarios to test and validate the plans

Earthquake Early Warning - Emergency Response

- When an earthquake is detected an early warning alert will be issued if the expected intensity of the earthquake is expected to exceed a warning alert threshold.

The screenshot shows the TURNkey dashboard with the following data:

- PROCEDIMIENTO PARA EL TERREMOTO: 13
- INCIDENTES: 12
- INFRAESTRUCTURA AFECTADA: 150
- OBSERVACIONES: 0

The 'TERREMOTOS' table contains the following data:

ID	FECHA	DESCRIPCIÓN	SÍMBOLO	EPICENTRO	PROFUNDIDAD	MAGNITUD	MAPA	ANÁLISIS	DETALLE
E22TB900204	2022/04/18 13:35	Earthquake 4/21/2022 3+1:21 AM (created by the engine)		38° 4' 48" N - 0° 42' 48" W	5,00 km	5,50 ML			

A warning alert is shown in the bottom right corner:

Earthquake is coming
ML: 6.1
Distance: -- Km

Earthquake Early Warning - Emergency Response

- The hospital can use this information to initiate immediate action to reduce the potential impact of the earthquake
 - Sounding an evacuation alarm; pause critical services; initiate action to protect vulnerable patients
- TURNkey will send notifications by email to the Hospital's Emergency Response and Recovery Teams advising them of the earthquake

The email notification is titled "NUEVO EVENTO SISMICO - HOSPITAL VEGA BAJA". The main text reads:

Habia un terremoto titulado "Earthquake 4/20/2022 9:34:14 AM (created by the engine)" (E22TB900204). Para consultar el evento haz click en el enlace <http://platform.earthquake-turnkey.eu/Event/Consult/521>. Por favor, haga clic en el enlace en el número de abajo para confirmar la lectura.

At the bottom of the notification, there is a button with the number "12" and an "OK" button. Below the button, it says "NUMERO MESSAGGIO: 98942191-91F1-4FDC-8B31-0D4C48D97431" and "DATA RICHIESTA: 4/20/2022 9:34:20 AM (UTC)".

Earthquake Early Warning - Activation of Disaster Management Plans

- Message requiring the receiver to attend the Emergency Command Group meeting
- Another message advising of the cancellation of all non-emergency appointments

The screenshot shows the TURNkey system interface for an earthquake event. At the top, it displays event details: ID E22T8900210, date 2022/04/18 12:56, epicentre 38° 4' 48" N - 0° 40' 48" W, depth 5.00, and magnitude 5.50 ML. Below this is a navigation menu with tabs for 'DATOS GENERALES', 'COMUNICACIONES', 'MENSAJES PUBLICOS', 'INFRAESTRUCTURA AFECTADA', 'AREAS GEOGRAFICAS AFECTADAS', 'ALARMA TEMPORARIA DE REPULSA', 'PROCEDIMIENTOS', 'ACCIDENTES', and 'ACTIVIDAD'. The 'COMUNICACIONES' tab is active, showing a table of messages:

FECHA	DESCRIPCION	HEMIFERIO (N/S)	ORIGEN/USUARIO	VER DETALLES
2022-04-21 05:41	Nuevo Evento		System Administrator	[Q]
2022-04-21 09:58	Cancellation Clases		Pablo Pérez	[Q]

A blue oval highlights the 'DESCRIPCION' column for the 'Cancellation Clases' message, which contains the text: 'Se cancelan todas las citas en el hospital para el 21 de abril por el terremoto'.

Earthquake Early Warning - Activation of Disaster Management Plans

- The hospital can initiate the distribution of other 'pre-defined' messages to key contacts and the public through email and via social media channels

The screenshot shows the TURNkey system interface for creating a public message. The event details at the top are: ID E22T8900204, date 2022/04/20 11:29, epicentre 38° 4' 29.47" N - 0° 40' 42.26" W, depth 5.00, and magnitude 6.50 ML. The 'MENSAJES PUBLICOS' tab is active. The form includes:

- NIVEL DE SEVERIDAD:** Grande (with social media icons for WhatsApp, Facebook, and Twitter).
- TITULO:** Hospital La Vega Baja: Comunicacion Urgente
- MENSAJE:** El sismo que ocurrió puede haber causado daños materiales en sus hogares. Hay que salir y acudir a los puntos de recogida a la espera de un control de estabilidad que se realizará en las próximas horas. Las escuelas han sido cerradas.

A blue oval highlights the social media sharing icons. Below the form is a table for 'MENSAJES PUBLICOS' with columns for ID, FECHA, TITULO, MENSAJE, and SOCIAL.

Earthquake Recovery

Rapid Response and Business Continuity Plans

27

Rapid Response to an Earthquake - Damage Estimates

- On detecting an earthquake TURNkey will produce very early shake maps and damage state zones for the most affected area.

28

Rapid Response to an Earthquake - Damage Estimates

- The Hospital can use the shake maps to get an early estimate of the potential damage state of their buildings and the potential impact these may have on service delivery (from previously ran simulations)
 - Set immediate priorities for Intervention Teams
 - Activate and monitor department level repair and recovery plans
 - Coordinate immediate response with civil protection
- If no appropriate simulation exists, a new simulation based on the actual earthquake characteristics can be generated

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Rapid Response to an Earthquake – Eyewitness Reporting

- After an earthquake TURNkey will monitor seismic activity and coordinate eye-witness observations of real-time damage to allow more reliable shake maps to be produced.
- Eye-witness observations are collected through the TURNkey app or entered directly through the GUI system

- Eye-witness information can be uploaded by 'authorised' people (e.g., hospital security, maintenance, facility management staff etc.)
- Eye-witness data is validated by the platform operator before is uploaded to the scientific engine

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Rapid Response to an Earthquake – Functional Performance

DATOS GENERALES

Descripción: Observación por parte del personal operativo

Evento: E227B9002 10 - 38° 4' 48" N - 0° 40' 48" W

Categoría de Infraestructuras: Medical Care Facility | Categoría: Hospital - Large | Infraestructura: HOSPITAL DE SALUD VEGA BAJA - XRAY

OTROS DATOS

Estado de daño: Grado 2 - Daño moderado | Pérdida de funcionalidad (%): 30

Número de muertos: 0 | Número de personas sin hogar: 0 | Número de refugiados: 0

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Rapid Response to an Earthquake – Recovery Activities

- TURNkey can coordinate and monitor progress of the response and recovery activities.

ID	DESCRIPCIÓN	ESTADO	TIPO	FECHA COMPLETADA	PROGRESO	VER ACTIVIDAD
P227B900032	Notificación y Activación del Plan	En curso	AUTOMÁTICO		5%	
	Recepción y transmisión de informaciones sobre el terremoto al Centro de Coordinación de Emergencias de la Generalitat	Completado	MANUAL	El terremoto es relevante y las informaciones han sido enviadas, ver documento adjunto	21-04-2022 10:06	alarm
	Notificar al Centro de Coordinación de Emergencias de la Generalitat	Para hacer	MANUAL			
	Establecer el nivel de emergencia	Para hacer	MANUAL			
	Activar el procedimiento para el nivel de emergencia	Para hacer	MANUAL			

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Aftershock Forecasts

- After an earthquake TURNkey will continue to monitor seismic activity and provide advanced warning of potential aftershocks

Aftershock Forecasts

- Hospital management can use this information to adjust their recovery activities
 - Temporarily suspend clean-up and repair work during a period of heightened risk
- TURNkey can also give an early warning of an after shock through the mobile app.
 - Those using the mobile app can send an I'm safe message once the aftershock has passed

The TURNkey FWCR Platform

A Decision Support Tool for CI and Businesses

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An Integrated Solution to Support DMP and BCP for CI and Businesses

- TURNkey is an early prototype system to help improve earthquake resilience in Europe
 - The primary users of the system will be those responsible for planning and coordinating the response to an earthquake.
 - Secondary users will be business and critical infrastructure organisations who can integrate TURNkey into their disaster management and business continuity planning

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Thank you for your attention

Questions or Comments

Further details of the TURNkey project can be found at www.earthquake-turnkey.eu

APPENDIX E

Expression of Interest letter from the municipality of Orihuela

Ayuntamiento de Orihuela

Orihuela 27th May, 2022

Letter of Commitment Project TURNkey GA. 821046

To whom it may concern,

The Orihuela City Council is actively involved in the activities of the project, by invitation of one of the Partners, the University of Alicante. The project itself and the results are of great interest for this City, due to the high seismic activity of the area.

Last 25th to 28th of April, the City of Orihuela hosted the Demonstration of the TURNkey platform, the Project management meeting and the stakeholders Workshop (Task 7.4). To this end, the City council has already invested significant human and economic resources: meeting hall, civil protection staff, sensor installation costs (Technical memory installation seismographs Exp. 8576/2022), etc..

With this letter, the City confirms and reinforces our interest in ensuring the project sustainability by supporting further activities that may be necessary to finish the Platform integration and full operation, even when the European Project has finished. Moreover, we will be glad to help the University of Alicante in the replication of our experience in other regional or national Municipalities. Sharing with them the advantages of the TURNkey system, we aim to add value to project results.

The person in charge of this initiative in the City Council is Mr. Francisco Masip Andújar, Orihuela City Emergency technician and his email is fmasic@orihuela.es, in case further information is needed.

Yours sincerely,

Guillermo Cánovas Vergel
Orihuela City Emergency Council

Ayuntamiento de Orihuela

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